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Processing of acoustic tomography data in the ACOBAR and UNDER-ICE experiments and development of new metadata structure for acoustic moorings

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Executive summary.

Processing of acoustic tomography data in the ACOBAR and UNDER-ICE experiments

Part I: Processing in the ACOBAR experiment

Chapter 1: Introduction

Acoustic tomography is a remote sensing technique to observe horizontally averaged ocean sound speeds. Using inversion techniques it can be used to measure horizontally averaged temperatures along observed sections. The principle of acoustic tomography is to send out an acoustic signal from a sound source and to record this signal by a distant receiver to determine the travel times of the signal. If the distance between source and receiver is known sound speeds can be calculated. Forward modeling, i.e. the acoustic modeling of a known ocean state along the observed path, is used to physically interpret the observed travel times.

Three main types of information are necessary to accurately measure signal travel times:

1. knowledge of experiment geometry:
The accurate positions of both source and receiver in the water column need to be known at all times. This part of the processing is described in [Chapter 2: Positioning of source and receiver instruments](#)
2. knowledge of experiment timing:
Accurate timing is necessary at both the source and the receiver. How this is achieved is described in [Chapter 3: Clock Corrections](#)
3. knowledge of source signal and receiver characteristics:
It is necessary to know the exact form of the source signal and the response curve of the receiver microphone to process the acoustic recordings. Using pulse compression and beam-forming signal arrivals can be identified from a noisy acoustic background. The estimator-correlator mechanism is used to improve the signal to noise ratio and reduce the problem of multiple arrivals from random scattering. The processing of the acoustic recordings is described in [Chapter 4: Processing of measured arrivals using matched filtering, beam-forming and the estimator-correlator](#)

Chapter 2: Positioning of source and receiver instruments

Knowing the accurate position of an instrument placed on a mooring at any time is a challenge. Moorings sway with the ocean current and an instrument placed at 400 m depth on a 1600 m long mooring might easily sway several hundred meters in the horizontal and more than 100 meters in the vertical. In Fram Strait horizontal mooring motions of 1km and vertical mooring motions of up to 250 m were observed. With conventional oceanographic moorings one is usually content to know the drop position, i.e. the position where the mooring was dropped from at the ocean surface. For the recovery of a failed mooring one might get a more accurate anchor position by triangulating the acoustic release at the bottom of the mooring. This is not sufficient for acoustic tomography. Instead the position of both source and receiver are monitored continuously by triangulating their position in the water column at every signal transmission. This is done by placing 4 transponders at the ocean floor around each mooring. An acoustic transducer mounted to the source and receiver units will send an acoustic signal to these transponders and measure the times of their return signals to triangulate its position relative to the transponders. 3 transponders are in principle enough to carry out the triangulation, the fourth transponder is for redundancy and error estimation.

The sea-floor transponders need to be positioned from the sea surface. For this purpose a positioning survey is carried out either after the deployment or before the recovery of the transponders, using a ship-based transducer. Ideally the triangulation of the transponders was carried out using 9 different ship positions for each transponder to get as accurate transponder positions as possible. Sometimes sea state and time constraints allowed fewer survey positions.

The exact location of the sound source and the receiver hydrophones varies somewhat from the mooring transducer used for the positioning, as they are further up or down the mooring cable. Using the known spatial configuration of the mooring this is corrected for by applying a vertical offset to the position of the various instruments relative to the mooring transducer. This implies that the inclination angle from mooring sway is neglected in this correction.

Therefore the following information is necessary for successful mooring positioning:

- Horizontal GPS position of the ship-borne transducer
- Depth of ship-borne transducer below the ocean surface
- Travel times of triangulation signals between ship-borne transducer and sea-floor transponders
- Travel times of signals between the mooring transducer and sea-floor transponders
- Sound speed profile at mooring position
- In case no GPS positions are available directly for the ship-borne transducer they need to be calculated using GPS positions at a known point on the ship and the orientation of the ship relative to the compass (ship gyro heading)
- drop position and depth at drop position
- signal detection time of the transducers and technical response time of transponders

As a first step the ship survey is analyzed. Ideally this can be done already onboard the ship. The ship survey data has to be cleaned up to remove multiple and false responses and bring the data in a form that can be automatically read into Matlab. Ship positions, survey travel times and until 2012 also ship

gyro heading data are collected by the Matlab routine `combine_survey_ship_test_f.m`, until 2012 the subscripts `ducerpos.m` (for Håkon Mosby) and `ducerpos_kvs.m` (for KV Svalbard) were necessary to convert the ship GPS positions to the ship transducer positions using ship gyro heading data. Until then also the ship geometry had to be known, more exactly the relative position of transducer and GPS antenna in ship coordinates. From 2014 on positions were measured by a new GPS directly above the transducer deployment position on the ships starboard side. Ship positions are calculated separately for each transponder response to correct for ship drift during the signal travel time. This is done by reading the GPS signal not at the time of the transducer signal, but at the mean time of transducer signal and received transponder response (transducer position at $t = (t_{\text{send}} + t_{\text{receive}})/2$).

A CTD, XCTD or XBT profile close to the mooring location needs to be processed, read into Matlab and, in case of an expendable profiler, quality checked and cleaned if necessary. The profile is extended to a maximum depth greater than the ocean depth by assuming constant temperature and salinity values below the lowest measurement. If only an XBT profile was available, a salinity profile needs to be guessed from older or regional data. A smooth sound speed profile is then calculated using the `make_ssp_mad.m` routine, which uses a least-square cubic spline for smoothing temperature and salinity, and the del Grosso formula to calculate sound speed from the smoothed temperature and salinity profiles. The data error estimate used for the cubic spline is 0.1 K for temperature and 0.001 for salinity.

This smooth sound speed profile and the depth of the transducer beneath the ocean surface are then used in the routine `zrayducer.m` to run a ray model, the results of which are interpolated onto a regular grid giving travel times from the transducer as a function of distance and depth. This travel time grid is then combined with the signal travel times and the initial estimates for the mooring position (drop position and ocean depth at drop position) to calculate a best estimate for the transponder positions on the sea floor. A position estimate is also calculated for the mooring anchor release if the necessary survey data exists. The calculation is done using the Matlab function `wimp.m` (called for every transponder and mooring by the script `wimpfoo.m`), using backward-forward filtering with iterated extended Kalman filters. The function `wimp.m` accounts for the transponder turn-around time or 0.003 s and the deck unit recognition time 0.0067 s, i.e. a total time delay of 0.0097 s for the two-way travel time. The program also gives an uncertainty estimate of the calculated transponder position that takes into account the geometry of the survey triangulation. Outlying survey data points can be discarded manually during the iterated estimation routine.

Figure 1: Flow chart of transponder survey processing

The second step is the positioning of the acoustic source and the hydrophones on the swaying mooring. The mooring position is surveyed by two-way navigation signal between the mooring and the transponders close to every acoustic transmission. The signal travel times are saved in the engineering file of the moored STAR (Simple Tomographic Acoustic Receiver) instrument. Combining the positions of the sea-floor transponders, the mooring geometry and a smooth sound speed profile from the mooring position, the moored instruments can thus be positioned at all times.

The script starfoo.m reads the engineering files of all moorings into Matlab and adds all necessary information about the moorings such as mooring name, instrument serial number, deployment year and the estimated position and depth of the mooring anchor. All of this information has to be filled in manually before running the script. The script output is called the engineering mat file. Different plot routines are available to display and quality check the engineering data. The script navpick.m reads out the two-way signal travel times between the mooring transducer and the four sea-floor transponders, the script also removes navigation signal echoes and allows the manual removal of bad data points.

For each sea-floor transponder a ray model script called zrayxpdr.m is run to calculate signal travel times that are interpolated on a regular grid as a function of horizontal distance and depth. This is similar to the ray modeling done for the survey processing that calculates travel times from the ship transducer (see above). The travel time grids calculated by zrayxpdr.m are then combined with the transponder travel times and the transponder positions from the survey to calculate the positions of the mooring transducer. This is done in the script navsolve3.m. This script takes also care of the transponder signal turnaround time of 0.003 s, and the STAR transducer detection time of 0.002 s. In addition it corrects -0.01s because the time axis reported by the engineering file is with respect to the trailing edge of the outgoing interrogation pulse, rather than the leading edge. The script also needs to read in the engineering mat file to take care of mooring meta data. As a last step, the script called mmotstar.m corrects for the vertical offset of the acoustic source and the hydrophones from the STAR navigation transducer. (The script mmotstar.m has actually been incorporated into the last few lines of the plotting script navplot.m). This is a somewhat simplified correction as it assumes no significant horizontal mooring sway between these different instruments. Using the maximum horizontal mooring sway of 1 km on a 2450 m long mooring, yields a sway angle of 24° from vertical. This means that the simplification can cause a 12 m error in the horizontal position of a hydrophone that is at 30 m vertical distance from the STAR navigation transducer.

Figure 2: Flow chart of mooring navigation

Chapter 3: Clock corrections

The timing of the sent and received signals needs to be very accurate as relative under-water sound speed variations are small. Unfortunately for the time being the most accurate timing devices are using too much electrical power to be used continuously in the moored instruments. Therefore there are two clocks included in the source and receiver electronics: a conventional crystal oscillator (MCXO) that is in continuous operation and a Rubidium atomic clock that is activated at regular intervals to provide an exact clock frequency. Every time the Rubidium clock is running a frequency comparison with the conventional clock is performed and the results are logged. Combining the information of both clocks, the clock drift of the conventional clock can be calculated and accurate timing can be reconstructed for the whole deployment period. To determine the correct start and end points of the time measurements both the conventional oscillator and the Rubidium clock are compared to an external timing signal in the laboratory at the beginning and end of each experiment. The external timing signal which is used is the timing signal of a GPS signal. The following data are therefore necessary to calculate the accurate timing for the mooring instruments:

- Comparison of GPS time signals to mooring internal oscillator in the laboratory before and after deployment
- Comparison of mooring Rubidium clock to GPS time signal in the laboratory before and after deployment, in reality this is done by comparing the mooring Rubidium clock to a deck unit Rubidium clock which in turn is compared to the external GPS time signal for a longer time period
- Comparison of mooring Rubidium clock to mooring internal oscillator at regular intervals during the deployment periods

For the clock correction processing the Matlab script `clockdata.m` combines all the measured time and frequency offsets described above to estimate the clock error of the crystal oscillator clock in the moored STAR instrument and the corresponding error uncertainty. The script reads the results of the internal STAR clock comparisons, i.e. mooring Rubidium clock vs. mooring internal oscillator from the engineering mat file of a mooring (this needs to be processed at this point, see above). The other clock comparisons have to be read in from manually written tables. The GPS vs. STAR internal oscillator latches are read from the file `stargpslatchleap.txt`, which in 2012 had to be adjusted to account for a leap second occurring on 31 June 2012. In a similar manner the results of the deck unit Rubidium clock comparison to the STAR Rubidium clock are read from the hand-written file `starduRbLatch.txt`. Finally the comparison of the deck unit Rubidium clock vs. external GPS time is done by calling the script `deckunitclock.m`, which compiles a log-file that has to be saved from the STAR deck unit. It is also possible to do this step in the field and instead just read in the mat file `clockDU`, which was saved then. The clock errors of the crystal oscillator clocks ranged during previous experiments from 0.2 – 1.4 seconds. The uncertainty of the clock error was in all cases less than 1 ms, except one mooring where the error uncertainty reached about 1.9 ms towards the end of the deployment period. After clock corrections are carried out, the remaining uncertainties resulting from clock errors are minor compared to the signal travel time uncertainties resulting from the uncertainty of the mooring position.

Chapter 4: Processing of measured arrivals using matched filtering, beam forming and the estimator-correlator

After the engineering data has been processed, the sound recordings can be analyzed with the aim of identifying (potentially several) ray arrivals of the frequency sweep signals emitted by the sound sources. Both for reasons of power consumption and because of environmental concerns it is desirable to limit the strength of the acoustic source signal. Using an exactly known signal of sufficient length and spanning different frequencies it is possible to detect such a signal against a noisy background despite its very moderate signal strength. The technique used to detect a known signal in a noisy background is called matched filtering or pulse compression. Popular choices for known signals are M sequences and frequency sweeps. Matched filtering is used to compress the 1-minute sweep signal to a signal pulse, thus optimizing the signal to noise ratio.

Matched filtering yields the arriving signal power at each receiver hydrophone. Still, in the case of multiple arrivals it can be difficult to distinguish between arrivals that are very close to each other in time. Using simultaneous data from several hydrophones at different depths it is possible to also get information about the incidence angle of incoming acoustic rays. This process is called beam forming and essentially converts the phase difference of arrivals between hydrophones at different depths to arrival angles by simple geometric reasoning. Beam forming thus provides information about the arrival angle of the wave front. Beam forming results are ambiguous with respect to the ambiguity of phase differences by multiples of 2π . Combining arrival times and angles, arrival peaks are detected by using a threshold of relative peak strengths compared to background levels.

The estimator-correlator accounts for the incoherence of a recorded frequency sweep by using sensible estimates of the coherency bandwidths of the received signal in time and frequency. It reduces the problem of random multiple arrivals caused by ray scattering. The estimator-correlator is smoothing the arrival peaks, which has the effect of reducing temporal resolution. However, if the estimates of time and frequency coherence are chosen correctly, this will be the most realistic description of the representative ray path disturbed by scattering. The main benefit of the estimator-correlator is the increase in signal-to-noise ratio.

If the pattern of arrival peaks is stable, i.e. essentially if the detected arrival peaks are not too close to each other or too variable in time, they can be tracked. This means that arrival peaks from tomography signals sent at different times can be identified as belonging to the same acoustic ray paths. Ideally it is possible to track several arriving rays for the entire experiment period. If this is the case than changes in measured travel times during the experiment can be interpreted as temperature changes along essentially stable ray paths.

The necessary information to carry out the matched filtering consists of:

- the shape of the source signal
- the transfer function of the receiver hydrophone
- the received acoustic recording

In addition the data resulting from the previous processing steps is collected to give the right timing for the detected acoustic signals:

- clock correction
- sound source and hydrophone positions (mooring motion)
- engineering mat file containing meta-data

For the beam forming we also need:

- the geometry of the hydrophone array
- sound speed profiles to convert phase differences between different hydrophones to arrival angles

For the estimator-correlator we need:

- estimates of the time and frequency coherence of the received signal

The Matlab script `tflax.m` collects all the necessary data for further processing (i.e. acoustic recordings, clock corrections, mooring motion information and smoothed sound speed profiles) and does the matched filtering of the acoustic recordings. It first converts the mooring motion into a time correction and combines this with the clock correction to provide accurate timing for all processed signals. After this the signal is demodulated and compressed using a matched filter of the known emitted frequency sweep. Finally, it uses the part of the recording that contains no received signals to estimate the background noise level for each hydrophone at this recording, and uses the signal-to-noise ration of the matched signals to the background noise level to detect peaks. A peak is detected when the SNR is above a threshold of 15 dB. This threshold was chosen because it gives a reasonable balance between false alarms and missed detections. The script saves a data file for each reception.

The second part of the signal processing is done by the script `tpfx.m`. This script combines the receptions of all four hydrophone at a mooring to do beamforming, i.e. to establish the arrival angle of the incoming wave fronts using the mooring geometry and the time delay of arrivals between different hydrophones. The contributions of each hydrophone are weighted to account for the different background levels of each hydrophone.

The same script then uses sensible values for frequency and time coherence bandwidths in an estimator-correlator mechanism to account for the incoherent nature of the received sweeps. This step is done last as it destroys the phase information of the acoustic pressure series that is needed for the calculation of the previous steps. The saved output of the signal processing contains the time, angle and magnitude information of the arrival peaks and information about the background noise level for each acoustic reception.

The calculated arrival peaks can be plotted as dot plots with `pkplot.m`. A final program (to be written) then tracks the arrival peaks that are assumed to correspond to stable acoustic rays.

Figure 3: Flow diagram of the acoustic data processing

Part II: Updates for the processing of the UNDER-ICE experiment

Chapter 1: Metadata

The UNDER-ICE project consists of many experiments and the data. Metadata facilitates in the discovery of the relevant information and results. Some metadata for the experiments is recorded by hand during the field experiments. The metadata provides basic information for the experiments and instruments and clarifies the relevance between the data for the experiments in processing and analyzing the UNDE-ICE data. It has to be extendable and manageable for the future additional experiments. In addition, the UNDER-ICE project has the duty to make measured data publicly available in an open-access data portal. Therefore all the metadata is required to be gathered, digitized, well-structured, and systematically ordered since it has to easily access, extract and understand the data. As a result, we decided to store the metadata in the Excel worksheets in each experiment and each sheet are linked by the mooring name. This provides a complete overview of all the necessary information related to the field experiment and processing for facilitating future publication of selected metadata.

1.1 Mooring metadata

Handwritten mooring metadata of the 2014 UNDER-ICE experiment was digitized manually and stored in the Excel worksheet *Metadata2014MooringL0.xlsx*. In the excel sheets, excel macro is assigned for data format for longitude and latitude columns. For instance, if '844.451' is put in a longitude cell, it is visualized as '008 44.451'E'. '-412.928' is showed as '004 12.928'W'. To activate the function, if ',' is used as a decimal separator in your excel setting, it is required to change to '.'. Then set macro feasible in the security alerts opening the excel file. The mooring metadata excel file consists of 7 sheets by each instrument; 'Mooring', 'STAR', 'transponder', 'sensor', 'acoRelease', 'ADCP' and 'anchor' (see Table 1). Variable names in each sheet are listed in Table 1 together with an example of their standard data style. The results of the transponder survey *srvLon*, *srvLat* and *srvDepth*, which are computed based among others on the Excel sheet *Metadata2014MooringL0.xlsx*, are appended to the *Metadata2014MooringL0.xlsx*, the resulting new sheet is then saved as *Metadata2014MooringL1.xlsx*.

The basis of the mooring metadata file is the *Mooring* sheet and each sheet is linked by the mooring names. For instance if the mooring name is specified, the position of the mooring is given from Lon and Lat columns based on the *name* key in the *Mooring* sheet and the corresponding transponder position is obtained from *dropLon* and *dropLat* based on the *mooring* key in the transponder sheet.

1.2 Survey metadata

The survey metadata file *metadata2014Survey.xlsx* includes three sheets; 'survey', 'transducer' and 'filePath'. The *survey* sheet is a center of the survey metadata file. Each sheet is linked by the *mooring* key and they are also connected to the *mooring* key in the mooring metadata file *metadata2014MooringL0.xlsx*.

Table1. mooring metadata

Sheet	Metadata name	Explanation	Example
Mooring	name	Mooring name	U11
	cruiseNo	KV Svalbard 2014	KVS2014
	Date	Drop date?	YYYYMMDD
	Time	Drop time	HHMM
	Lon	Longitude of drop position of mooring	008 45.068'E
	Lat	Latitude of drop position of mooring	77 53.909'N
	cDepth	Corrected depth of drop position	1413 (m)
	depth_surface_unit	Depth of the mooring from the surface	347 (m)
	benthos_locator	serialNo of Benthos Transponder on Strongback	55881
	xeosKilo_locator	XEOS KILO Platform ID No.	SW6812281
	catPinger	EdgeTech at pinger ID No.	48539
	source	Acoustic source	NERSC-1
STAR	serialNo	STAR serial number	133
	mooring	Mooring name	U11
	Depth	Depth of DSTAR receiver from the surface	456.02 (m)
	date	Start date of STAR schedule??	YYYYMMDD
	situation	Current STAR status	Recoverable/expendable
transponder	serialNo	transponder serial number	41927
	mooring	Mooring name	U11
	freq	Transponder frequency	11 (Hz)
	dropLon	Longitude of drop position of transponder	088 44.41'E
	dropLat	Latitude of drop position of transponder	77 54.42'N
	uDepth	Uncorrected depth of transponder	1448 (m)
	srvLon (L1)	Longitude of survey position of transponder	088 44.555'E
	srvLat (L1)	Latitude of survey position of transponder	77 54.472'N
sensor	serialNo	sensor serial number	501
	mooring	Mooring name	U11
	Type	Module type	HM00
	Depth	Depth of sensor	467 (m)
acoRelease	serialNo	acoRelease serial number	62872
	mooring	Mooring name	U11
	modelNo	Acoustic release model no.	Benthos865A
	Test	Tested at depth:	500 (m)
	intDreq	Interrogate frequency	8.5 (Hz)
	reqFreq	Reply frequency	10 (Hz)
	dsiableCom	Disable command	
	enableCom	Enable command	G
	releaseCom	Release command	C
ADCP	Time	Time until release falls asleep	12 hours
	serialNo	ADCP serial number	16071
	mooring	Mooring name	U11
anchor	Type	Long/short-range, upward/downward looking	up
	serialNo	anchor serial number	1001
	mooring	Mooring name	U11
	Freq	Received frequency	11 (Hz)
	dropLon	Longitude of drop position of anchor	008 45.086'E
	droplet	Latitude of drop position of anchor	77 53.909'N
	uDepth	Uncorrected depth of anchor	1449 (m)
	srvLon (L1)	Longitude of survey position of anchor	008 44.875'E
	srvLat (L1)	Latitude of survey position of anchor	77 54.045'N
srvDepth (L1)	Survey depth of anchor	1402.135 (m)	

YYYY: year, MM: month, DD: date, HH: hour and MM: minute

Table2. survey metadata

Sheet	Metadata name	Explanation	Example
Survey	mooring	Mooring name	UI1
	date	Date of the survey	YYYYMMDD
	pMax	Round depth value greater than the greatest possible transponder depth	1700 (m)
Tran-ducer	mooring	Mooring name	UI1
	depth	Depth of ship-borne transducer below the sea surface	11.30 (m)
File Path	mooring	Mooring name	UI1
	ctd	CTD File name	cast/XBT_C3_00063.mat

YYYY: year, MM: month and DD: date

Chapter 2: Updated processing of transponder survey

It is necessary to rebuild the processing routines of the ship survey for the correct transponder positions as part of the establishment of an integrated metadata repository. Hardcoded information spread over many processing routines makes it difficult to manage the information and easy for errors to occur by multiple manual copies of the information. It is expected that a large volume of data will be delivered from the future UNDER-ICE experiments. Therefore it is necessary to build a processing system, which loads all the required information from one place, the metadata repository. This allows the streamlining of the processing and reduces the risk of human errors. This chapter describes the updated processing routines that compute the correct transponder positions by loading all the required information from one place and updating the information.

2.1 Create survey date file combining ship GPS positions and survey travel times

The ship travel time data and ship GPS positions have to be cleaned up to remove multiple and false responses. This process has to be done manually. The cleaned data of survey travel times and ship GPS positions are named like *DDMM_YYYY_clean.txt* and *YYYYMMDDKVS_clean.log* respectively. 'YYYY', 'MM' and 'DD' represent year, month and date of the survey date loaded from the survey metadata file.

Ship positions are selected separately for each transponder response to correct for ship drift during the signal travel time. They are calculated by reading the GPS signal at the mean time of transducer signal and received transponder response (transducer position at $t = \frac{t_{send} + t_{receive}}{2}$).

The Matlab script ***combine_survey_ship.m*** finds a ship GPS position corresponding to each survey travel time and create arrays for ship positions (longitudes, latitudes), travel times and frequencies. First the survey date is loaded from the survey sheet in *metadata2014Survey.xmls*. The date is used to specify the file names for survey travel time and ship GPS position. The *dorplInfo* table, which has 5 variables (dropLon, dropLat, serialNo, freq. and instrument), is then created by loading data from transponder and anchor sheets in *metadata2014MooringLO.xml*. The survey travel time and ship GPS position files are read by each line and the data are stored in Matlab structure arrays as *surveyData* and *positionData* respectively. The *surveyData* has *surveyTime* and *travelTime* as the fields. The *positionData* includes three fields as *time*, *lat* and *lon*. Search for the best matched *positionData.time* corresponding to the *surveyData .surveyTime* and *surveyData .travelTime*. The *positionData.lat* and *positionData.lon* corresponding to the best matched *positionData.time* are concatenated with *surveyData* as *surveyData.lat* and *surveyData.lon*. The *surveyData.travelTime*, *surveyData.lat* and *surveyData.lon* are save as *srvy.tt*, *srvy.lat* and *srvy.lon*. Moreover a frequency array is created from *dorplInfo.freq.* and saved as *srvy.rfreq*. The *srvy* structure array is then saved in *KVSYYYYMMDD.mat* or *KVSYYYYMMDD_anchor.mat*.

2.2 Compute ray travel times

The Matlab script ***make_sspmad.m*** computes a smooth sound speed profile based on CTD data whose file name is obtained from the *filePath* sheet in *metadata2014Survey.xmls*. Extract the pressure, temperature and salinity data from the CTD data and remove corrupted data. Since it is assumed that the pressure is equal to the depth (1decibar = 1meter), 'pressure' is used to synonyms with 'depth' in the script. Create a vector *prw* which has values from 0 to a maximum pressure (or depth), given by *pMax* in survey sheet in *metadata2014Survey.xmls*, with an equally-spaced 1decibar (or 1meter). The temperature and salinity data are interpolated onto the vector *prw*. The Matlab function *medfilt1()* is applied to the temperature and salinity data and then the data are smoothed with the function *lsspl()*. The *lsspl()* does a least-square cubic spline fit of the data. The data error estimation used for the cubic spline is 0.1K for temperature and 0.001 for salinity. The function *aog_vsdg()* computes the sound speed based on the smoothed temperature and salinity profile by applying DelGrosso formula. The function *aog_eos80()* computes and returns the density from the pressure, temperature and salinity profiles. Using the density, pressure and latitude from the CTD data, the function *aog_pr2dynhgt()* calculates the depth. The sound speed and depth data are saved as *cw* and *zw* arrays in a *Station%s.mat* file (*%s* is the mooring name).

The Matlab script ***zrayducer.m*** applies a ray model using the smoothed sound speed profiles and transducer depths in *metadata2014Survey.xmls* as the input arguments. The depth of the transducer means depth beneath the ocean surface. In the script, the function *zray()* is called and it computes and returns a structure array *zry* which includes ray range, ray depth, ray travel time, ray momentum, ray

weighting, ray arc length and ray weighting. The ray travel time is interpolated onto a uniform grid in *zrayducer.m* and the interpolated travel time and its depth, and range grids are saved into a *zryt%s.mat* file (%s is the mooring name) as *zryt*, *zryz* and *zryr* arrays. The *zryz* and *zryr* contain the grid coordinates.

2.3 Compute survey position and depth

The Matlab script *wimpfoo.m* loads the survey date, drop position (longitude and latitude), uncorrected depth, frequency, survey information and smoothed sound profiles from *metadata2014Survey.xml*, *metadata2014MooringL0.xml* and mat files for survey overview and ray travel time arrays respectively. The survey date is used to determine the name of the survey overview mat file (*KVSYYYYMMDD.mat* and *KVSYYYYMMDD_anchor.mat*). In the script, drop position and uncorrected depth are passed to the function *carter()*. The *carter()* applies Carter table correction to echosounder data that is collected assuming sound speed = 1500 m/s. Lookup tables *BOUNDARY2.DAT* and *CORRECTN2.DAT* are used for the correction. The calculated correct depth and Carter correction area are returned *wimpfoo()*. Then *wimpfoo()* passes the corrected depth, drop position and mat file names for survey overview smoothed sound speed profiles and ray travel time arrays to *wimp()*. The *wimp()* accounts for the transponder turn-around time or 0.003(s) and the deck unit recognition time 0.0067(s), i.e. a total time delay of 0.0097(s) for the two-way travel time. The program also gives an uncertainty estimate of the calculated transponder position that takes into account the geometry of the survey triangulation. Outlying survey data points can be discarded manually during the iterated estimation routine. The results computed in *wimp()* are returned to *wimpfoo()* as a structure array *xpos* and are saved in *xpos%s.mat* (%s is the mooring name). The estimated positions (longitude and latitude) and depth are saved in a csv file ('*srv2014_%s_transponder*' or '*srv2014_%s_anchor*') in the same directory with the metadata. The csv file is then imported into *Metadata2014MooringL0.xlsx* manually and the excel file is renamed *Metadata2014MooringL1.xlsx*. It is recommended to use the transponder positions from the Matlab file for subsequent processing steps to retain optimal accuracy.

Chapter 3: Future metadata and processing updates

The metadata for the clock correction (see Part I, chapter 3) and the processing of measured acoustic arrivals (see Part I, chapter 4) will need to be collected and organized in the same manner as demonstrated for the mooring and survey metadata. The processing routines for the positioning of the acoustic sources and receivers, as well as the clock corrections and the processing of measured acoustic arrivals will need to be updated to account for the use of metadata Excel sheets. It is desirable that also these processing scripts will be streamlined to prepare for the large amount of data expected in the UNDER-ICE experiment. The processing script for the positioning of the acoustic sources and receivers and the clock corrections also need updates due to changes in experiment design from the ACOBAR to the UNDER-ICE experiments: instead of hydrophones cabled the STAR control units now separate hydrophone modules are used, which communicate with the STAR unit through an inductive link. The processing script updates will also be an opportunity to reduce position errors due to mooring sway as they were described at the end of Part I, chapter 2.